
Therapeutic Effects of *Hemidesmus indicus*- An Overview

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Abstract From the time immemorial, herbal medicines have been used globally as curative agent for variety of ailments as they are having few or no side-effects. *Hemidesmus indicus* belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae and is commonly known as Indian sarsaparilla and East Indian sarsaparilla. It is distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical parts of India, especially in upper Gangetic plains, Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, and South India. This plant contains the following: Pregnane glycoside, Coumarinolignoids, β -amyirin acetate, α -amyirin, β -amyirin, Lupeol acetate, β -sitosterol, Hexadecanoic acid, Hexatriacontane, Lupeolactosylate, etc. It is a perennial, slender, twining undershrub with woody and fragrant rootstock. *Hemidesmus indicus* possesses following activities analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiarthritic, antioxidant, antiacne, antipsychotic, anti-diarrhoeal, wound healing, antiulcer, larvicidal, antivenom, antihyperlipidaemic, antimicrobial, anti-carcinogenic etc. The aim of this review is to provide an overview of comprehensive account of the phytochemical investigation, therapeutic potential and pharmacological studies of the plant *Hemidesmus indicus*.

Keywords *Hemidesmus indicus*, herbal medicines, analgesic, Indian sarsaparilla, Anamtamul

Introduction

Herbal plants are being used globally since the time immemorial, either as a single drug or in combination to provide new remedies as they are having few or no side-effects. Herbal medicines are easily available and are cheaper than other medicines [1].

Hemidesmus indicus belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae and is commonly known as Indian sarsaparilla and East Indian sarsaparilla [2].

Root is the most useful part of *Hemidesmus indicus* which is having different pharmacological activities like antimicrobial, anti-enterobacterial, anti-acne, anti-oxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, etc [3].

Taxonomical Classification [4]

Kingdom : Plantae
Division : Magnoliophyta
Class : Magnoliopsida
Order : Gentianales
Family : Apocynaceae
Subfamily : Asclepiadoideae
Genus : *Hemidesmus*
Species : *Indicus*

Vernacular names [5]

Sanskrit	: DhawalaShariva, Gopa, Gopakanya, Krushodari, Sfota, Shyama, Gopavalli, Lata, Aasfota, Chandana
English	: Indian Sarsaparilla
Hindi	: Salsa
Marathi	: Anantvel, Uplasari, Maeenmool
Tamil	: Nannari
Gujarati	: Anantmul
Kannada	: Anamtamul
Assam	: Ananatmul
Bengali	: Anantmul
Malayalam	: Nannaari
Oriya	: Suguddimalo
Persian	: Ushba
Urdu	: Salsa
Telugu	: Sugandhi

Distribution

Hemidesmus indicus is distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical parts of India, especially in upper Gangetic plains, Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, and South India. It generally occurs on sub-ravine slopes, twining on shrubs and trees [6].

Morphology**Habit**

H. indicus is a perennial, slender, twining undershrub with woody and fragrant rootstock [6].

Leaves

The leaves are simple, opposite, short-petioled, very variable, elliptic-oblong to linear-lanceolate, variegated, and white above and silvery-white pubescent beneath [7].

Flowers

Flowers are having greenish yellow to greenish purple colour outside and dull yellow to light purplish colour inside. Calyx is deeply five lobed.

Corolla gamopetalous and about twice the calyx.

Stamens are five in number, inserted near base of corolla with a thick coronal scale [8].

Stem

The stem is numerous, slender, terete, thickened at the nodes and of a deep purple or purplish brown colour with the surface slightly ridged [9].

Root

Roots are woody and aromatic [10].

Phytochemical Constituents [11, 12]

Phytochemical constituents isolated from different parts of the plant are as below:

Roots:

- Pregnane glycoside: Hemindicusin
- Coumarinolignoids: Hemidesmin-1 and Hemidesmin-2
- β -amyirin acetate
- α -amyirin
- β -amyirin
- Lupeol acetate
- β -sitosterol

- Hexadecanoic acid
- Hexatriacontane
- Lupeolactosylate
- Oil: crystalline matter, glucose, hemidesmol, hemidesterol, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzaldehyde, resin acid, glucoside, α -amyrin triterpene, β -amyrin triterpene, and benzaldehyde

Stem:

- Glycosides: Indicine and Hemidine
- Pregnane glycoside: Hemidescine and Emidine
- Pregnaneoligo glycosides: demicunine and heminine.
- Desinine
- Indicusin
- Medidesmine
- Hemisine
- Demicine
- Steroidal compounds: Calogenin-3- α - β -D-digitoxopyranosteroid, desminine steroid, hemisine steroid
- Triterpenoids: 3-keto-lup-12-ene-21->28 olide triterpene, lup-12-ene-3- β -ol-acetate triterpene

Leaves:

- Coumarinolignoids: hemidesminine, hemidesmin-1, hemidesmin-2
- Flavonoids: hyperoside and rutin
- Tannins (2.5%)

Flowers:

- Flavanoid glycosides viz. Hyperoside, Isoquercetin and Rutin

Pharmacology**Anticarcinogenic activity**

The roots decoction of the plant showed cytotoxic effect on HepG2 cells. The extract exhibited inhibition of the growth of tumour in the skin of mouse and hence it can be considered as a potent chemopreventive agent [13]. A decoction comprised of *Nigella sativa* seeds, *Hemidesmus indicus* root bark and *Smilax glabra* rhizome has potential to provide protection against chemically induced hepatocarcinogenesis [14].

Anti-inflammatory activity

In rats acute and subacute inflammation was induced by carrageenan, bradykinin, S-hydroxy tryptamine and when it was treated with ethyl acetate root extract of *Hemidesmus indicus* it exhibited its anti-inflammatory potential [15].

Analgesic activity

Significant inhibition of writhing response, decrease in licking response in acetic acid-induced writhing response and Eddy's hot plate method were observed in Swiss albino mice when treated at different doses with hydro-alcoholic extract of *Hemidesmus indicus* [16].

It was assumed that the analgesic effect of the extract may be due to either its action on the inhibition of the production of algogenic substances or the inhibition at the central level of the transmission of painful signals [17].

Anti-pyretic activity

The anti-pyretic (brewer's yeast induced pyrexia) effect was evaluated in Wistar albino rats which was measured as percent decrease in body temperature [18].

Antioxidant activity

The aqueous extract of whole plant of *Hemidesmus indicus* exhibited significant free radical scavenging activity which indicates that the plants extract has the potential source of antioxidants and thus could prevent many radical diseases [19].

Antimicrobial activity

Combination of aqueous root extract of *Hemidesmus indicus* along with barks of *Ficus bengalensis* and *Pterocarpus marsipium* exhibited antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* [20].

In agar well diffusion test, methanolic and ethanolic root extract of *H. indicus* exhibited maximum zone of inhibition against *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio cholera* [21].

Antiacne activity

The roots extract of *H. indicus* has strong inhibitory effect on *Propionibacterium acne* and *Staphylococcus epidermis* which are responsible for acne vulgaris [22].

Antivenom

The methanolic extract of *Hemidesmus indicus* has the potential to significantly neutralized lethality and haemorrhagic activity, defibrinogenation in albino rat and mouse [23].

Anti-ulcer activity

The alcoholic extract of *H. indicus* root showed significant reduction in ulcer index at different concentrations [24].

Antidiarrhoeal activity

Aqueous and ethanolic extract of roots of *H. indicus* significantly reduced the diarrheal effects in rats by decreasing faecal droppings, intestinal transit and intestinal fluid secretion [25].

Conclusion

From the time immemorial, herbal medicines have been used globally as curative agent for variety of ailments. Studies have revealed that *Hemidesmus indicus* possesses following activities analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiarthritic, antioxidant, antiacne, antipsychotic, anti-diarrhoeal, wound healing, antiulcer, larvicidal, antivenom, antihyperlipidemic, antimicrobial, anti-carcinogenic etc. Further studies and higher efforts are required to identify the novel clinical properties of this plant and to identify and isolate the particular compound which responsible for the specific therapeutic activities.

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